

CHANGES IN THE INCIDENCE OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA AND ALLERGIC RHINITIS IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN IN 2021–2023: A RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract: The aim of the study was to examine changes in the incidence of bronchial asthma and allergic rhinitis in various regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan over a three-year period. A retrospective analysis of statistical data was conducted for 2021–2023. It was found that the highest concentration of cases is observed in cities and industrialized areas. The identified differences by region require further epidemiological analysis.

Keywords: bronchial asthma, allergic rhinitis, Karakalpakstan, incidence, epidemiology.

Introduction: Allergic respiratory diseases, such as bronchial asthma and allergic rhinitis, represent a significant medical and social problem, especially in regions with specific climatic and environmental conditions. According to the WHO, more than 300 million people worldwide suffer from bronchial asthma. The Republic of Karakalpakstan, located in an area of ecological distress (including due to the drying up of the Aral Sea), is a unique model for studying the dynamics of allergic diseases.

Materials and Methods: The analysis was based on official statistics from healthcare institutions in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The study covers data for 2021, 2022, and 2023 across 17 administrative units. Registered cases of bronchial asthma and allergic rhinitis were assessed. **Method:** Retrospective descriptive analysis with elements of comparative statistics. **Study results:** Overall, the incidence of bronchial asthma in the republic was: 1,711 cases in 2021, 1,574 in 2022, and 1,870 in 2023. The incidence of allergic rhinitis was 3,981 in 2021, 3,727 in 2022, and 3,931 in 2023.

The highest rates were recorded in the following districts: Nukus (city) — asthma: 210 (2023), rhinitis: 464; Kungrad — asthma: 594 (2023), rhinitis: 545; Khodjeyli — an increase from 78 to 254 asthma cases over three years.

Results: Factors influencing the high incidence rate include: environmental stress (dust, salts, dry climate); urbanization and industrialization; access to medical care and diagnosis. The increase in the number of diagnosed cases may reflect both a real increase in incidence and improved detection rates. Migration processes and the possible impact of epidemics on the healthcare system should also be taken into account.

Conclusion: The data indicate a high and stable prevalence of bronchial asthma and allergic rhinitis in the republic. The identified regional differences should be taken into account when developing regional prevention and medical surveillance programs. Additional epidemiological and clinical laboratory research is recommended.

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